

ROBIN KIRKPATRICK
DANTE: THE DIVINE COMEDY
Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004. xiii, 118 pp.

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It is a certain challenge to introduce students to the world of *The Divine Comedy*. In this concise introductory guide, Kirkpatrick skilfully succeeds in addressing a wide array of student concerns about crucial elements of Dante's work. His attention to historical context and Dante's evolution as a writer throughout all of his writings is a great help to any student confronting the *Comedy* for the first time. Touching on the effects created by rhetorical figures and metrical devices used by Dante to evoke certain emotions, as well as introducing important studies and names, such as Croce, Singleton, Foster and Auerbach, Kirkpatrick subtly makes the reader aware of the complexity of the *Comedy*, while providing a masterful introduction to the greater world of Dante Studies.

Kirkpatrick divides his book into four chapters, followed by a synthetic guide to further reading. The first discusses different approaches to the reading of the *Comedy*. The second deals with Dante's evolution through his early works, with an analysis of *Inferno* II, the limitations of Virgil, the importance of Beatrice and Dante's place in the history of Italian literature. In this chapter, Kirkpatrick also discusses the significance of the comedic register, the challenge of maintaining continuity among the *canti*, and the flexibility of the *terzina*. The third analyzes the *Inferno*, *Purgatorio* and *Paradiso*, breaking the three *cantiche* down into groups of thematically related *canti*. The last chapter looks at the effect the *Comedy* had on Boccaccio, Michelangelo and T. S. Eliot, so to give the student an indication of the considerable impact it has had throughout history, in different environments.

One of the first difficulties that the reader of the *Comedy* faces as they begin to follow Dante on his supernatural journey is the deciding where to place the line between fact and fiction. This difficulty arises because Dante is concerned with Truth at every turn. God grants his journey so that Dante may be the prophet who guides humankind to salvation. The language used by Dante is one of "exact science and logical demonstration" (p. 2), rooted in historical fact. Dante's poem also has an instrumental function: to restore the dignity the Florentines robbed Dante of and to change the world of his time for the better. Kirkpatrick reveals the *Comedy*'s complexity even in this first affront. However, he is also keen to note, the seemingly rigid conclusions Dante arrives at are also meant to produce questions; even Dante wrote in the pursuit of self-knowledge and this pursuit is always plagued by doubt. The

student should therefore, not merely accept Dante's attempt at defining truth, but question him, in order to appreciate the staying power of such a masterpiece.

Kirkpatrick focuses on the poetic and narrative characteristics of the *Comedy*. The *Comedy* stands as the ultimate maturation of Dante's perpetual experimentation. In choosing narrative poetry as the vehicle for his epic, Dante not only takes great strides from his previous lyric style, but also from the philosophic model he was developing with the *Convivio*. Dante discovers in narrative poetry the way to edify and convey truth to humanity. Where philosophy can remain in the realm of pure thought, the act of storytelling allows him integrate philosophy with a practical activity. Dante turns philosophy into action, action aiming at involving and hence redeeming the reader.

The character Virgil is central to Dante's storytelling. Dante chose for his guide a pagan poet, passing over other potential guides in the forms of St. Thomas Aquinas, St. Francis, Boethius and Aristotle. Beginning with the *Vita Nova*, Dante perceived the journey to truth as a pilgrimage, and then with the influence of the *Aeneid* and Aeneas, as an epic journey, which means "to exercise skill in the negotiation of the hazards and the plotting of directions until we arrive at 'the port and city' we were meant to reach" (p. 8); and only Virgil displays the compassion necessary to dignify the value that Dante placed on terrestrial life. As a poet, Virgil manages to assimilate many of the characteristics of the four other figures, which is to say that only narrative poetry successfully combines all the aspects that Dante wishes to expound in his contribution to the salvation of humanity, in the act of storytelling. This is not to say Virgil is without his limits: while it is Virgil that inspires Dante's style, it is Beatrice who puts his journey in motion.

Beatrice is the cause of the changes Dante desires to make, as well as a bearer of numerous other meanings. Kirkpatrick demonstrates how Beatrice is responsible for the personal and stylistic changes Dante will pursue, beginning with the *Vita Nova* and concluding in the *Paradiso*. Beatrice inspires Dante's faith in human nature and God, and impels his journey to moral perfection. Through the mourning and circumstances of Beatrice's physical death, he understands how death is merely a passageway to eternity. These internal changes are reflected in the experimentation of the *Vita Nova*, through the sonnets, *ballate* and *canzoni*, that will cede to the *Comedy's canto* and *terzina*.

Kirkpatrick uses the figures of Beatrice and Virgil to discuss the issue of literal and allegorical meaning. The student will find Kirkpatrick's vindication of the literal level and explanation of the allegorical level very reassuring. He notes that Dante himself placed a strong emphasis on the literal level and that although an allegorical reading, at times, is possible, the

use of allegory is not consistent. Where allegory is possible, such as in the figures of Beatrice and Virgil, Dante plays out their allegorical meanings in their literal, concrete actions: Virgil is Reason, but this derives from his actions, responses and role as Dante's guide; Beatrice inspires Dante to change, she represents perfection, salvation and Truth, as shown in her reprove of Dante when they meet on Mount Purgatory. Kirkpatrick sees allegory in relation to action and warns against an overly structured reading.

Kirkpatrick clearly leads the reader through Dante's evolution as a writer, linking the personal and intellectual changes that transform Dante from the introspective lyric poet of the *Vita Nova* to the extroverted narrative poet of the *Comedy*. He identifies the central role the *Vita Nova* plays as a preliminary to the *Comedy*. He explains the philosophical and stylistic maturity Dante displays in the *Convivio*, as well as the civic environment and secular influences that inspired him. Kirkpatrick shows that although it is difficult to foresee the *Comedy* as the direct result of Dante's continual experimentation and intellectual growth, he had actually developed the skills and ideas necessary to compose it.

Directly related to Dante's experimentation are his contributions to vernacular literature and the history of the Italian language. Kirkpatrick draws attention to Dante's emulation of the classical tradition of love poetry and its revitalized Provençal form. Dante eagerly partakes in this regenerated poetic tradition, but realizes that he must make his own contribution and develop his own poetic voice. In an easily accessible manner, Kirkpatrick explains the development of Dante's artistic and philosophic voices closely follows the development of the vernacular and his defence of it in *De Vulgari Eloquentia*.

The *Comedy* is Dante's attempt to define the relation between God, Creator of the Universe, and the human being, His creation. The slow path to truth Dante follows through the hundred *canti* is consistent with his other works, in that, through a modification of the courtly motif of love from a distance, Dante uses a variety of 'screens' that have to be progressively superseded in order to arrive at an understanding of God that will eventually dismantle all former ways of reasoning. Before the Godhead, Dante recognizes the limits of human reason and the insurmountable multiplicity of reality. The *Inferno* explores God negatively, "through what he is not and through what he does not intend his creation to be" (p. 57), intrinsically making God a judge and Dante a poet of judgement. The *Purgatorio* is about transition and the difficulty of the journey, both the present supernatural one and our mortal one, that prompts us to the discipline of wilfully travelling the long, painful road to truth. Kirkpatrick's discussion of the different personalities Dante encounters and his comparison of the *Paradiso* to the *Inferno* and the *Purgatorio*, are an excellent help to understanding the theoretical range of the

Comedy.

Kirkpatrick provides students with a wonderfully well-written guide. His attention to historical, linguistic and metrical issues intertwines succinctly with his lucid presentation of a wide array of the literary aspects of the *Comedy*. One of the features of this guide that the student will find most helpful and engaging is Kirkpatrick's habit of plainly asking the questions the student will ask and then responding to them. In this way, Kirkpatrick embraces the concerns of the student and resolves some of the primary questions that, in other guides, go unaddressed. Students will find the modern approach of this guide highly valuable as they prepare to explore a world that can appear most distant.

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